

The Coronian Pride: The Existential Soliloquy of Corona

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I (Corona) am the crown of the world. Human beings are no more the summit of the world. I am something and human beings are nothing. Human beings dread at my sight. Their power, ego, energy, strength, capacity, achievement, and qualification are nothing before me. As I rule, all human beings tremble. In my regime, all human beings feel scary and frightful.

Social Distance

My existence has shaken their very being, their very existence. At my might there are weak. It looks human beings can find no way out. They have given in totally to my rule. Now, I have become their greatest adversary. They have all kinds of anger and frustration against me. They want to kill me. They want to destroy me. They are trying to annihilate me. But in vain!

Human beings have manufactured most powerful weapons, arms and ammunitions but all of them are rendered useless before my sight; no weapon can destroy me. Human beings have become absolutely helpless. They are nervous; they live in constant anxiety, tension and worry. They ask: When do you leave us? But, I cannot leave human beings. I am human

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friendly. Human beings are most comfortable shelter and nest for me. I find no other hamlet than human beings. I will rule the human world. I will control human beings.

I know human beings are social beings. As social beings, they come together, live together and eat together. But today, I have become a threat to their social life. Human beings were greeting each other with casual hand shake and now with my arrival shake hand has become a forgone gesture. Human beings were comfortably eating and socializing in the restaurants, open places and exchanging their happiness and joy. With my advent, everything has come to stand still. I have become a stumbling block to their social life. Now I govern them with a rule of social distance.

The Lonely and Masked Existence

The word “Lockdown” so far rarely used, has become a daily word. Ever since I took control of the world, nations, states, villages are all submitted to the law of lockdown. Oh yeah, today I take pride in teaching humans a new word and through it a new world in which they have to live.

Men were conscious of their handsomeness and women of their beauty. They used to go to beauticians and aesthetic clinics and spend a lot of time for a fairy tale looks and self-admirations. But with my sway, men and women have totally withdrawn themselves from these so called good looking activities and are content with their natural appearance.

Human beings could identify each other face to face easily from a distance. But today my dominion amidst them has masked their identity. Their natural beauty is hidden. Their appearance is vizard or a disguise. There is no one to appreciate their beauty. No one to commend about their personality. Everyone has become a masked reality. The natural is hidden. I have masked their real beauty.

Human beings had manifold food habits. They were happy and elated with this part of their life. Ever since my arrival, they have

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found decadence in food; they look no more for the variety contained “menu card”. They live in a constant fear of morrow’s sustenance. My rule over them has made their movements swift to hunt for the livelihood. People have changed their lifestyle from multiple to scanty.

Conclusion: The Crown of the World

Today, I am proud to say that I could create trepidation in every human person. The most powerful persons in the world are living in burrows. They feel safe nowhere. If they go home, I am there, If they go to office I am there, If they try to run in the waters, I am there. If they go abroad, I am there. People are simply caught within themselves; they do not have an inch of courage to peep out. All people in the world, rich and poor, haves and have not’s, rulers and the ruled, white and black, yes, all have become feeble and defenseless. Their life is paralysed; all human beings are confused. They want to put an end to my reign but they have not yet succeeded. I remain as the crown of the world. I am CORONA. The proud one! Challenging yours!.